

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

THE FREE RECTUS FEMORIS MUSCLE FLAP AS A VERSATILE FLAP OPTION FOR LOWER EXTREMITY RECONSTRUCTION

O. A. Ajani,^{1,2} G. O. Onyejekwe,¹ T. O. Osisanya,¹ O. S. Ilori,³ M. F. Alimi,⁴ N. Okoh,⁵ M. N Salihu⁵

¹Department of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, National Orthopaedic Hospital, Igbobi, Lagos;

²Division of Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery, Department of Surgery, Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos; ³ Department of Surgery, College of Health Sciences, Ladoke Akintola University of

Technology, Ogbomoso; ⁴Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, National Orthopaedic Hospital, Igbobi, Lagos; ⁵Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, National Orthopaedic Hospital, Dala, Kano.

Corresponding Author

O. S. Ilori, Department of Surgery, College of Health Sciences, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso.

Email: osilori@lautech.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: Reconstruction of extensive lower extremity defects, especially those of the distal third of the leg, continues to pose a reconstructive challenge to plastic surgeons. Free flaps have been described as the gold-standard for these reconstructions, with commonly preferred options including the free anterolateral thigh and latissimus dorsi flap. In our experience, the free rectus femoris flap is a good alternative, owing to its technical ease of harvest, satisfactory pedicle length and calibre, and minimal donor site morbidity. We describe our experience with this flap in twenty-one patients.

Methodology: This was a retrospective study conducted in the Departments of Plastic Surgery of the National Orthopaedic Hospital, Igbobi, Lagos; Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, both in Lagos, Nigeria, and National Orthopaedic Hospital, Dala, Kano; over a three-year period, between January 2019 and December 2022. All surgeries had the first author (AOA) as the lead surgeon. Biodata, indication, site of defect, pedicle length and calibre, duration of surgery, recipient vessels and post-operative complication profile were all assessed.

Results: A total of twenty-one patients were included in the study; 18 males and 3 females, with age range of 8 to 54 years. The majority of the defects were post-traumatic (81.8%), followed by post-sequestrectomy defects for osteomyelitis management (13.6%), while post- extirpation of tumours accounted for the least (4.5%). The average duration of flap harvest was 40 minutes, while average duration of entire surgery was 335 minutes. There was full flap survival in 59% and partial flap loss in 27.7%. Complete flap loss was recorded in 18.2% of cases. Donor site complications were minor and included superficial wound infection and hypertrophic scarring.

Conclusion: The free rectus femoris flap is a good free flap option in lower extremity reconstruction. Its predictable pedicle location and dimensions, superficial location in the anterior thigh, hence the consequent ease of harvest, and minimal donor site morbidities make it a reliable alternative to the other more popular free flap options.

Keywords: Rectus femoris, Microvascular free flap, Lower limb reconstruction

Introduction

Soft tissue coverage of lower extremity defects continues to pose a challenge to the reconstructive plastic surgeon. Wounds in the distal third of the

leg pose an even greater challenge due to the paucity of muscle bulk and poor vascular supply.¹ Free flaps have been described as a goal-standard for lower third leg defects.^{1,2} The understanding

and description of the perforator concept has added perforator flaps to the armamentarium of plastic surgeons, for complex leg defects.³

Some of the most commonly utilized free flap options for lower extremity reconstruction include the anterolateral thigh free flap, superficial circumflex iliac perforator free flap and the latissimus dorsi free flap for more extensive defects.⁴

The rectus femoris free flap has also been known as a good option for lower extremity salvage, owing to its ease of dissection, constant anatomy, good pedicle length and calibre, and minimal donor site complications.⁵ There is paucity of information on the use of free rectus femoris flap in Sub-saharan Africa especially in Nigeria. The free flaps used in other similar studies done in Nigeria were mainly Anterolateral thigh flap and Latissimus dorsi flap.

We present our experience with this flap in twenty-one patients managed at the Departments of Plastic Surgery of the National Orthopaedic Hospital, Igbobi, Lagos; Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Ikeja, Lagos; and National Orthopaedic Hospital, Dala, Kano, all in Nigeria, over a three- year period, between January 2019 and December 2022.

Methods

This retrospective study was conducted at the Plastic Surgery Departments of the National Orthopaedic Hospital, Igbobi, Lagos; Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos; and National Orthopaedic Hospital, Dala, Kano. All surgeries had the first author (A.A.O) as lead surgeon and were performed between January 2019 and December 2022.

All procedures included microsurgical free rectus femoris flap coverage of lower extremity defects. Defects were optimized pre-operatively by debridement and optimal wound care. All patients had pre-operative magnetic resonance angiography for delineation of recipient vessels. Two-team approach was adopted to reduce intra-operative time. A team was involved in the harvest of the flap while the second team was involved simultaneously in the preparation of the recipient site and the dissection of the recipient vessel. Rectus femoris flap harvests spared the distal 7cm

tendinous segment of the muscle with subsequent repair and re-enforcement of the quadriceps complex. All microvascular anastomoses were performed by the first author. End-to-end anastomosis was done to the anterior tibial artery in majority of cases, with end-to-side done to posterior tibial artery in 4 cases where the anterior tibial artery was severely damaged.

Data collected included; demographics, indication for surgery, site of defects, total duration of procedure, flap outcome and donor site complications.

All patients signed detailed informed consent forms, including approval for use of clinical photographs.

Results

A total of 22 flaps were performed in 21 patients, of which there were 18 (85.7%) males and 3 (14.25) females. One male patient had bilateral lower extremity flap reconstruction. The age range of the patients was 8-54 years, distributed thus; 3(14.2) patients were 45 years and above, 14(66.7%) were between 25-44 years and 4(19%) were less than 25 years.

Post-traumatic defects constituted majority of the defects; 18(81.8%), followed by post-sequestrectomy defects accounting for 3(13.6%) of the defects, and post-sarcoma extirpation defect accounting for 1(4.5%) defect. The commonest site of defect was on the distal third of the leg in 15(68.2%) of cases, followed by the dorsum of the foot in 4(18.2%) and lastly 3(16.7%) cases involving the sole of the foot

The average duration of the procedures was 5 hours 35 minutes.

There was full flap survival in 13(59%) cases, partial flap loss in 6(27.7%) cases. Complete flap loss occurred in 4(18.2%) cases. All limbs with flap failure were salvaged with combination of negative pressure wound therapy and split-thickness grafting.

Donor site complications include wound infection in 2(9.1%) patients, hypertrophic scarring in 3(13.6%) patients and hematoma collection in 1(4.5%) patient. All patients regained full active range of extension at the knee joint at six months follow up.

Table 1: Summary of the patients' clinical features

S/N	Sex	Age (years)	Location of the defect	Indication for the flap	Complications
1.	M	25	Sole of the right foot	Post-traumatic defect	Complete flap loss
2	M	45	Distal two-third of the left leg	Soft tissue defect and segmental bone loss due to trauma	skin graft epidermolysis
3	F	40	Distal third of the right leg	Post sequestrectomy defect	Nil
4	M	54	Dorsum of the left foot	Post-traumatic defect	Complete flap loss
5	F	22	Sole of the right foot	Post-traumatic defect	Partial flap loss
6	M	39	Distal two-third of the left leg	Post excision of soft tissue sarcoma	Tumour recurrence
7	M	28	Sole of the left foot	Post-traumatic defect	Partial flap loss
8	M	43	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
9	M	42	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
10	M	44	Distal third of the right leg	Post sequestrectomy defect	Nil
11	M	8	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Partial flap loss
12	F	37	Dorsum of the right foot	Post-traumatic defect	Complete flap loss
13	M	48	Bilateral distal leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
14	M	19	Distal third of the left leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
15	M	41	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Partial flap loss
16	M	27	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
17	M	41	Distal two third of the left leg	Post sequestrectomy defect	Partial flap loss
18	M	24	Dorsum of the left foot	Post-traumatic defect	Complete flap loss
19	M	31	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil
20	M	35	Dorsum of the left foot	Post-traumatic defect	Partial flap loss
21	M	40	Distal third of the right leg	Post-traumatic defect	Nil

Case 1

A 45-year-old man presented with extensive distal two-thirds of left leg soft tissue defect and segmental tibial loss following high velocity motor-vehicular crash. He had initial wound debridement and skeletal stabilization with an external fixator device, with insertion of a bone cement spacer (Figure 1a). He subsequently

underwent rectus femoris free flap coverage of the defect, with full flap survival (Figures 1b and 1c).

Case 2

A 40 year old woman with post-sequestrectomy defect of the distal right leg, with expose bone cement spacer (Figure 2a). She had rectus femoris free flap coverage with anastomosis to the anterior tibial artery (Figure 2b). Her recovery was uneventful with full flap survival (Figure 2c).

Figure 1a: Extensive distal third of left leg soft tissue defect, with exposed bone cement spacer and external fixator device

Figure 1b: Immediate post-operative result showing healthy-looking free flap in situ with overlying meshed split-thickness skin graft

Figure 1c: Two weeks post-operative outcome with full flap survival and minimal epidermolysis of the meshed skin graft

Case 3

A 39 year old man with soft tissue sarcoma of the mid and distal left leg. He had en-bloc wide local excision with immediate rectus femoris free flap coverage of defect, leaving an extensive defect in the distal two-thirds of the leg (figures 3a, 3b). He had full flap survival and was discharged home 4 weeks post-operatively. He however defaulted on

planned adjuvant radiotherapy, and re-presented 8 months later with advanced recurrence, necessitating limb amputation.

Figure 2a: Extensive post-osteomyelitis sequestrectomy soft tissue defect on distal right leg with exposed bone cement spacer

Figure 2b: Rectus femoris free flap after successful anastomosis to the anterior tibial vessel system

Figure 2c: Two weeks post-operative outcome with full flap survival

Discussion

Reconstruction of lower extremity defects continues to pose a challenge to plastic surgeons. Free tissue transfer remains the gold-standard for extensive distal third defects where there is paucity of local tissue and precarious blood supply.^{1,2}

Figure 3a: Extensive Hemi-circumferential post-tumour extirpation defect with exposed bone and muscles in the distal two-thirds of the left leg

Figure 3b: Excised soft tissue sarcoma specimen

Figure 3c: Post free flap coverage with rectus femoris muscle and meshed SSG, with good outcome.

Several free flap options have been described. Muscle flaps, including latissimus dorsi, sartorius, rectus abdominis and rectus femoris flaps have been extensively described in literature. Muscle

flaps are known to provide bulk and fill dead spaces, while improving vascularity to the area⁶. To reduce donor site morbidity, a shift towards free perforator flaps has been adopted in recent times, with the anterolateral thigh flap being a work horse flap in lower extremity reconstruction⁷. These perforator flaps obviate the need for muscle harvest, thus eliminating the complications associated with motor deficit following muscle harvest. The major draw-back however of the preferred anterolateral thigh (ALT) flap is the tedious pedicle dissection⁷.

The rectus femoris flap is a component of the knee extensor (quadriceps) mechanism. It is the most superficial muscle of the quadriceps muscles and has a fairly constant pedicle. Its superficial location makes its harvest easy to perform within a short period of time, hence reducing intra-operative duration, especially in single microsurgeon instances like ours⁸. Studies, including those by Wei F.C et al have shown that preserving the distal 6-7 cm of the tendon and re-incorporating same into the quadriceps mechanism results in minimal to no problems with knee extension^{8,9}. Any minimal deficit is easily compensated for by the other quadriceps muscles and improves with physical therapy.

Gelidan A.G.⁹ described the use of the rectus femoris flap as a salvage procedure in a failed attempt at a free ALT flap.

The major drawback of the flap is its relatively short pedicle length of about 5cm, with vessel calibre of 2-2.5mm. Hence, dissecting to the origin of the pedicle is critical to preserve as much length as possible. Also important is obtaining a good length of recipient vessel to ensure an easy anastomosis away from the zone of injury is critical.

Our study showed minimal donor site complication, similar to the study by other authors.^{5,7,8,9}

Conclusion

The rectus femoris flap remains a good free flap option owing to its ease of dissection, minimal donor site morbidity and constant pedicle location. Pedicle dissection should proceed as far proximal as possible to obtain a satisfactory length.

Acknowledgment

We acknowledge the support of the Medical Directors of the three tertiary institutions where this research was conducted for their support toward the development of microsurgical expertise in the country. The heads of departments' consultants, residents and indeed the entire surgical, anaesthesia and nursing teams who ensure optimal outcomes for these complex reconstructions are greatly appreciated

Declarations

Funding

No external funding was obtained for the research.

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Code availability

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Authors' Contributions

OAA contributed to the conception, literature search, design of the work and the final write-up. GOO, TOO, OSI, MFA, NO and MNS all contributed to the literature search, design of the work and final write-up.

Ethics approval

All patients signed detailed informed consents, and consented to the use of their photograph for educational and publication purposes. Ethical approval was not obtained.

Consent to participate

Obtained from participants.

Consent for publication

Obtained from all authors.

References

1. Bajantri B, Bharati RR, Sabapathy SR. Wound coverage considerations of the lower third of leg. *Indian J Plast Surg.* 2012; 45(2): 283-290.
2. Zeiderman MR, Pu LLQ. Contemporary approach to soft tissue reconstruction of the lower extremity. *Burns Trauma.* 2021;9 Published online 2021 Jul 30.
3. Mohan AT, Sur YJ, Zhu L, Morsy M, Wu PS, Moran SL et al. The concepts of propeller, perforator, keystone, and other local flaps and their role in the evolution of reconstruction. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2016; 138:710e-29.
4. Acar MA, Gulec A, Aydin BK, Erkokak OF, Yilmaz G, Senaran H. Reconstruction of foot and ankle defect with free anterolateral thigh flap

in pediatric patients. *J. Reconstr. Microsurg.* 2015;31(3):225-232

5. Wei CY, Chuang DC, Chen H.C, Lin C.H, Wong SS. The versatility of the free rectus femoris muscle flap as an alternative flap. *Microsurgery.* 1995;16(10):698-703

6. Rinker B, Valerio IL, Stewart DH, Pu LQ, Vasconez HC. Microvascular free flap reconstruction in pediatric lower extremity trauma; a 10-year review. *Plast. Reconstr. Surg.* 2005;115(6):1618-1624

7. Hsieh CH, Yang JC, Chen CC, Kuo YP, Jeng SF. Alternative reconstruction choices for ALT flap dissection in which no sizable perforator is available. *Head Neck.* 2009;(5):1002

8. Wong C, Ong YS, Wei FC. Revisiting vascular supply of the rectus femoris and its relevance in the host of the ALT flap. *Ann. Plast. Surg.* 2013;71(5):586-590

9. Gelidan AG. Salvage of planned ALT flap with rectus femoris free flap for pediatric lower extremity reconstruction; a demonstrative case report. *Int. J. Surg. Case Rep* 2018;51:67-70.